

Socioeconomic Status, Parental Expectations, and Student Motivation as Predictors of Academic Performance of Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Kenneth Budiongan , Godivah Irish Reyes , Krisha Liporada ,
Melanie Galo , De Mar M. Bangeles
Graduate School, Holy Cross of Davao College, Philippines

Suggested Citation

Budiongan, K., Reyes, G.I., Liporada, K., Galo, M., & Bangeles, D.M.M. (2024). Socioeconomic Status, Parental Expectations, and Student Motivation as Predictors of Academic Performance of Grade 12 Senior High School Students. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 385-396.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).32](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).32)

Abstract:

This study aims to explore the interplay of socioeconomic factors, parental expectations, and student motivation in predicting academic success. Utilizing a quantitative research design, the study collected data from 99 senior high school students through structured questionnaires. The findings indicate that students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds generally have access to better educational resources, leading to higher academic performance. Parental expectations were found to significantly motivate students, fostering a supportive learning environment and encouraging academic excellence. High levels of student motivation were also identified as crucial for academic success, promoting effective study habits and resilience. The research underscores the importance of a

holistic approach in educational policy, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to support students from disadvantaged backgrounds. By understanding the influence of family environment on student motivation and performance, educators and policymakers can develop strategies to enhance educational outcomes. This study contributes to the broader discourse on educational equity, highlighting the role of socioeconomic status and parental involvement in shaping student achievements. It calls for collaborative efforts between schools and families to create conducive learning environments that support all students' academic endeavors.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Socio-economic Status, Parental Expectations, Student Motivation, Educational Equity.*

Introduction

Motivation has always been associated with academic performance in school. Academic performance is mostly dependent on student motivation, which is what propels engagement, tenacity, and accomplishment in learning endeavors. Students' path through various academic undertakings is greatly influenced by their innate drive to learn as well as outside variables that may influence their aptitude for

learning. Motivation includes both the eagerness to start things and the perseverance to finish them, especially in the face of difficulties. When students are young, they live mostly in the homes of their parents or guardians. This is the beginning of a critical time when they undergo significant development and change. This stage includes social, emotional, mental, and physical development, and the family environment acts as a testing ground for these complex shifts. The

household has a greater effect when things are challenging. Students negotiate the complicated nature of their changing identities and face the challenges of their academic journey inside the comfortable walls of their homes. The people who make up the household—parents, guardians, or other relatives—have a significant impact on the students' motivation and well-being.

A study in China found that parents' education has various effects on their kids' academic success. It implies that parental expectations and socioeconomic status are strong indicators of students' academic success. According to the study, a moderately unfavorable association exists between parental expectations and family wealth in the structural models of mathematics and the ability to solve problems. This is likely due, in part, to the fact that family wealth and income are two different conceptions, Long & Weiguo Pang (2016).

Rumbaoa (2022). As stated in the study conducted at the University of Santo Tomas, Manila regardless of a student's socioeconomic status, academic achievement tends to decrease when a student belongs to a higher social class; on the other hand, academic achievement increases when a student belongs to a lower social class. This could be brought on by the various incentive methods utilized by the students. Students in the middle or high socioeconomic status have greater welfare than students in the low socioeconomic status, so they might not have as many reasons to put in the time and effort to learn, which lowers their GPA relative to students in the low socioeconomic status who strive for a better life.

In the local setting, home environment characteristics were discovered to have a considerable impact on students' academic achievement. These include the size of the family, the parents' educational background, their economic standing, the accessibility of learning resources, the kind of Internet connection, and Internet connectivity. Every one of these elements of the family environment has a big impact on how well youngsters learn. Liquigan (2023).

It is crucial to look into how student motivation and socioeconomic factors interact to determine senior high school student's academic achievement. Through the identification of gaps in outcomes and the development of targeted interventions to benefit students from disadvantaged backgrounds, this research is essential to the advancement of educational equity. These insights can help policymakers create evidence-based policies, and schools can better allocate resources and customize programs to meet the specific needs of various student populations. Acknowledging how family expectations and involvement affect students' motivation promotes cooperative efforts between parents and schools. Personalized learning tactics can be used with the help of instructors who can better engage and support individual students by thoroughly understanding the many motivational elements. Early detection of students who may experience academic difficulties allows for prompt interventions, which contributes to long-term success. By addressing socioeconomic concerns, researchers and policymakers help create equal chances for all students. Education is a means to social mobility. This all-encompassing strategy not only promotes academic achievement but also the general growth and well-being of students, which helps to create a competent and competitive labor force on a worldwide basis.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to determine the socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and motivation of students in achieving their academic performance, more specifically, this study seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the level of socioeconomic status of the grade 12 senior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Parental income;
 - 1.2. Parents occupation; and
 - 1.3. Parental education?
2. What is the level of parental expectations as perceived by the grade 12 senior high school students?

3. What is the level of motivation of the grade 12 senior high school students?
4. What is the level of academic performance of the grade 12 senior high school students in terms of grade point average?
5. Is there a combined significant relationship between the predictors of socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation on the outcome variable academic performance among senior high school students?
6. Is there a combined significant influence between the predictors of socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation on the outcome variable academic performance among senior high school students?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no combined significant relationship between the predictors of socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation on the outcome variable academic performance among senior high school students.

H₀₂: There is no combined significant influence between the predictors of socioeconomic status,

parental expectations, and student motivation on the outcome variable academic performance among senior high school students

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1977), which believes that people will analyze information actively and will consider the effects of their actions (Saul Mcleod, 2024). According to this idea, people will acquire knowledge by watching other people. Students from various socioeconomic backgrounds will be able to observe and absorb the educational practices and attitudes displayed by their framework offered by social cognitive theory will aid in understanding the complex interactions that will exist between parental expectations, student motivation, academic families and communities in the context of their academic achievement. A theoretical achievement, and socioeconomic background. Through its consideration of social aspects of behavior and learning, the theory will advance our comprehension of how outside factors will mold students' educational experiences and results.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Method

In this chapter, the methods and procedures used in this study are discussed. This chapter

includes the research design, respondents of the study, research instruments, ethical considerations, data collection, and data analysis.

Research Design

The research design aimed to fulfill the objectives of the research and find solutions to the research questions. This research used a quantitative design to offer a clear view of the predictors of academic performance of senior high school students and guarantee the validity and reliability of the research. In the quantitative design, descriptive statistics were used to indicate the scores' distribution using a few indices. Structured questionnaires were conducted for data collection through a simple random sampling distribution of questionnaires to senior high school students. This method was preferred because it was fast and economical. The sequential execution of the research was delineated into distinct steps: firstly, the random selection of senior high school students to participate in the survey; secondly, the assessment of students based on their responses to the questionnaire; thirdly, the voluntary nature of participation in the survey; fourthly, completion of the questionnaire, which was expected to take approximately 3 to 4 minutes; and finally, the discussion of results upon the conclusion of the survey.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were 99 senior high school students 18 years old and above who know the income of their parents. The method that was used to identify the respondents is through random sampling, where everyone is given a chance to participate in this study.

Research Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a quantitative survey instrument. Survey questions were given to the respondents. The research instrument aimed to collect both quantitative data for statistical analysis and qualitative insights to provide a holistic understanding of the interplay between socioeconomic factors, parental expectations, and student motivation in predicting academic performance among senior high school students.

Ethical Consideration

In this study, ethical considerations were given importance and thoroughly followed. This

research was administered and anchored to the ethical principles and code of conduct by REC. The researchers guaranteed that the collected data within the study was kept confidential and fully secured as part of their responsibilities.

Data Collection

The researchers conducted their study using an adapted survey questionnaire. The questionnaires were designed to assess student motivation as a predictor of the academic performance of senior high school students in the study. The questionnaires contained confidential questions that were not shared with the respondents. The researchers ensured that the questionnaires were clear and easy to understand. They also provided instructions on how to answer the questions accurately. The survey questionnaires were disseminated personally by the researchers, allowing them to communicate with the respondents and gather their responses easily.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data of this study, the researchers used the following tools: Mean, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, and multiple linear regression.

Results and Discussions

Table 1. The Perceived Socioeconomic Status among Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Indicator	Mean	Description
Parental income	3.89	High
Parents occupation	3.91	High
Parental education	3.98	High
Overall	3.89	High

The findings reveal that most students consider their family income to be above average. High parental income is typically linked to better access to educational resources, extracurricular activities, and a supportive learning environment, all of which can enhance academic performance. Additionally, the high average score for parents' occupations implies that many

students' parents have reputable and economically stable jobs. Such occupations can elevate a family's socioeconomic status, fostering an environment conducive to academic success. Furthermore, the highest average score among the indicators shows that students believe their parents are highly educated. Parents with advanced education levels are more likely to value education, set higher academic expectations, and have the capability to support their children's education effectively. The combined mean score, reflecting high perceptions across all indicators, indicates a strong socioeconomic status among the student group. This high socioeconomic perception is vital as it often leads to better academic support, higher parental expectations, and increased student motivation.

The data presented in Table 1 implies that high parental income and occupational status generally provide better financial resources for educational needs, such as quality schools, tutoring, and enrichment activities. Higher parental education often results in greater involvement in a child's education and a better grasp of academic requirements. Parents with a higher socioeconomic status tend to set higher academic expectations for their children, which can encourage students to achieve better results. The combination of a supportive, resource-rich environment and high expectations likely boosts student motivation, a key factor in academic success.

Results of the analysis would support the study conducted by Davis-Kean, Tighe, and Waters (2020) that socioeconomic status (SES), educational attainment, parent occupation, and family income—is a powerful predictor of children's developmental outcomes. Parents' educational attainment provides a foundation that supports children's academic success indirectly through the beliefs and expectations that parents hold for their children, as well as the cognitive stimulation that parents provide in and outside of the home environment. Additionally, in a study conducted by Munir, Faiza, and Daud (2023), they mentioned that the Socioeconomic position appears to affect academic

performance. Higher socioeconomic students fare better academically.

Table 2. Level of Parental Expectations as Perceived by the Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Variable	Mean	Description
Parental Expectations	3.72	High

As shown in the table above, grade 12 senior high school students have a high level of parental expectations (mean = 3.72) as predictors of academic performance.

The result implies that a high level of parental expectation can significantly predict and influence the academic performance of Grade 12 students by providing motivation, support, and a conducive learning environment. This could mean that parents with high expectations often encourage their children to strive for excellence, providing motivation and reinforcing the importance of education. This encouragement can boost students' self-confidence and drive them to perform well academically. Parents who expect high academic achievement tend to set clear, high standards and goals for their children. They emphasize the importance of education and help their children set and achieve specific academic goals, which can lead to improved performance.

Similarly and Tatlah (2019) conducted a study on "Parental Expectations and its impact on academic achievement of students mediated by academic self-concept at secondary level" and found out that parents have high expectations regarding their children's academic achievement. Thus, Parents are expected to extend high expectations about the academic achievements of their children. This furthers the study conducted by Lindberg, Yıldırım, Elvan, and Öztürk (2019) parents' expectations are not based on the current situation of the youth's academic success but based on the parents' aspirations.

Table 3. Level of Motivation of Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Variable	Mean	Description
Motivation	4.08	High

As shown in the table above, grade 12 senior high school students have a high level of motivation (mean = 4.08) as a predictor of academic performance.

The result implies that a high level of motivation is a significant predictor of academic performance in Grade 12 students. This could mean that a high level of motivation drives them to set and achieve goals, put forth sustained effort, and maintain a positive and proactive approach to learning. Motivated students are more likely to excel academically due to their determination, effective study habits, and resilience in the face of challenges. Motivation can foster resilience, allowing students to cope with academic stress and setbacks. Motivated students are more likely to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than insurmountable obstacles, leading to a more positive and proactive approach to their studies. Motivated students often display a positive attitude toward school and learning. They participate actively in class, seek help when needed, and engage in extracurricular activities that enrich their educational experience.

Results of the analysis would support the study conducted by Muhammad, Abu Bakar, and Sadiq (2021) that motivation serves as a good predictor of students' performance. Based on the findings from the study, a strong relationship exists between motivation and Students' academic performance. Similarly, students' motivation serves as a yardstick in predicting their performance. Similarly, the study conducted by Sabanal, Reputana, Palwa, & Labandero (2023) stresses that among the factors considered for motivation, only performance goals posted a moderate level, while other aspects, such as achievement goals, active learning strategies, learning environment simulations, science learning value, and self-efficacy, registered high levels. Furthermore, the study revealed the students' motivation toward

learning and academic performance were positively and significantly correlated.

Table 4. Academic Performance of the Grade 12 Senior High School Students in Terms of Grade Point Average

Academic Performance	Grade Scale	f	%
Outstanding	90 - 100	16	16.20
Very Satisfactorily	85 - 89	40	40.40
Satisfactorily	80 - 84	43	43.40
Fairly Satisfactorily	75 - 79	0	0.00
Do not meet the expectation	Below 75	0	0.00
Overall		99	100.00
Average Academic Performance	85 - 89		Very Satisfactory

The data in Table 4 provides a summary of the academic performance of Grade 12 senior high school students based on their grade point averages (GPAs). The table categorizes the students' GPAs into different performance levels and indicates the frequency (f) and percentage (%) of students falling within each category. A minority of students, 16.20%, achieved an outstanding GPA, indicating a high level of academic excellence among this group. Close to half of the students 40.40%, fall within this category, demonstrating that a significant number of students are performing at a very satisfactory level. The largest portion of students 43.40%, are performing satisfactorily. This indicates that the majority of students are achieving grades that are considered satisfactory or better. No students fall within the fairly satisfactory range, suggesting that all students are performing above this level. Similarly, no students are performing below expectations, indicating that all students meet or exceed the minimum satisfactory performance level.

The academic performance data shows that a significant proportion of students are achieving at satisfactory or higher levels, with no students performing below satisfactory (below 75 GPA). This distribution might indicate that the students come from relatively stable socioeconomic backgrounds, with access to necessary educational resources and support systems that

contribute to their academic success. The high levels of academic performance, particularly the 16.20% of students achieving outstanding GPAs and the 40.40% achieving very satisfactory GPAs, could reflect high parental expectations. When parents have high academic expectations for their children, students are often more motivated to meet these expectations, leading to higher academic achievement. The absence of students in the lower performance categories suggests that parental expectations and support might play a crucial role in maintaining high academic standards. The high levels of academic performance, particularly the 16.20% of students achieving outstanding GPAs and the 40.40% achieving very satisfactory GPAs, could reflect high parental expectations. When parents have high academic expectations for their children, students are often more motivated to meet these expectations, leading to higher academic achievement. The absence of students in the lower performance categories suggests that parental expectations and support might play a crucial role in maintaining high academic standards.

The academic performance data reflects a generally high level of achievement among Grade 12 students, likely influenced by favorable socioeconomic conditions, strong parental expectations, and high student motivation. This alignment with the predictors identified in the research article underscores the importance of these factors in driving academic success.

Higher parental expectations did not consistently lead to the type of involvement that directly correlates with academic achievement, Yamamoto and Halloway 2010. According to Şengönül (2022) in his study, the educational engagement shown by parents with lower socioeconomic status is crucial because it helps mitigate or eliminate the disadvantages faced by children from less affluent and less educated families, reducing their risk of academic failure. Kwarteng et, al 2022, concluded in their study that parents' socioeconomic status, particularly their education, occupation, and income levels, plays a significant role in determining students' academic performance.

Predictors	Pearson Correlation	Strength of the Relationship	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Socio-Economic Status	.052	Weak	.606	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Parental Expectations	.153	Weak	.130	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Student Motivation	.400**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Outcome: academic performance
****.** Correlation is Significant at 0.01 Level (2-tailed)
N = 99

Figure 2. Test of Relationship Between Socioeconomic Status, Parental Expectations, and Student Motivation to the Academic Performance of Senior High School Students

As shown in the table above there is a significant relationship between students' motivation to the academic performance of senior high school students. Meanwhile, the socio-economic status

and parental expectations show no significant relationship to the academic performance of the grade 12 senior high school students.

The r-value of socio-economic status .052 means that there is a weak strength of the relationship between socioeconomic status and academic performance. This could imply that socioeconomic status has a relatively minimal impact on students' academic outcomes. In other words, differences in family income, parental education level, and occupational status do not strongly predict or explain variations in how well students perform academically. This finding implies that other factors, such as parental expectations, student motivation, teaching quality, and school resources, might have a more significant influence on academic performance than SES. Therefore, while SES still has some effect, it is not a major determinant of students' academic success. The r-value of parental expectations .153 means that there is a weak strength in the relationship between parental expectations and academic performance. An r-value of 0.153 suggests that while there is a positive relationship between parental expectations and academic performance, it is relatively weak. This means that variations in parental expectations are not strongly associated with variations in academic

performance among the students. The r-value of student motivation .400** means that there is a moderate relationship between student motivation and academic performance; this implies that student motivation has a noticeable and meaningful influence on how well students perform academically. A moderate correlation indicates that there is a consistent, but not overwhelming, association between higher levels of motivation and better academic outcomes.

Correlation analysis examined the relationship between socioeconomic status and academic performance. Higher socioeconomic positions appear to affect academic performance and have fared better academically (Munir et al., 2023). Moreover, research by Davis-Kean (2005) explored the indirect effects of SES on academic performance through parental involvement and educational expectations. The study concluded that while SES influences the resources available to students, its direct effect on academic outcomes is limited. Instead, the educational aspirations and involvement of parents, regardless of SES, were found to be more critical determinants of student performance.

Model Summary	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE
1	.421	.177	.152	.66863

<i>Coefficients</i>					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	SE B	β		
1					
(Constant)	2.948	.579		5.092	.000
Student Motivation	.577	.137	.482	4.216	.000
Socio-Economic Status	-.244	.154	-.172	-1.590	.115
Parental Expectations	-.016	.108	-.016	-.148	.883

Figure 3. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Predictors to the Academic Performance of Senior High School Students

As shown in the table above, the results of the regression indicated that the predictors explained 17.7% of the variance [$R^2 = .177$, $F(3,95) = 6.833$, $p = .000^b$]. It was found that Student Motivation ($\beta = .577$, $p = .000 < .05$)

significantly predicted academic performance among the respondents. Furthermore, Student Motivation encompasses 15.4% of the 17.7% variance of the total model [$R^2 = .154$, $F(7,97) = 17.957$, $p = .000^b$].

Further analysis would suggest that for every unit increase in student motivation, there is an approximately .577-unit increase in academic performance. The analysis indicates that Student Motivation plays a significant role in predicting academic performance among the respondents, explaining a considerable portion of the total variance in the model.

A study by Gottfried, Fleming, and Gottfried (2001) supports this, showing that students with higher intrinsic motivation tend to have better academic outcomes, including higher grades and greater retention rates. The current study's findings align with this body of literature, emphasizing that student motivation significantly predicts academic performance. The β coefficient of .577 indicates a strong positive relationship, reinforcing the notion that motivated students are more likely to excel academically.

Furthermore, a study by Richardson, Abraham, and Bond (2012) conducted a meta-analysis of the correlates of academic performance, identifying motivation as a key predictor. They reported that motivation-related constructs, including goal orientation and self-efficacy, had substantial predictive validity for academic performance, accounting for a significant portion of the variance in students' grades and test scores. The regression analysis in the current study, which indicates that student motivation explains 15.4% of the total model variance, is consistent with these findings. It demonstrates the substantial role that motivation plays in academic success, suggesting that interventions aimed at enhancing student motivation could yield significant improvements in educational outcomes.

Additionally, the study by Wolters and Rosenthal (2000) explored the relationship between students' motivational beliefs and their use of cognitive and metacognitive strategies. The findings revealed that students with higher motivation were more likely to use effective learning strategies, leading to better academic performance. This suggests that motivation not only directly influences academic achievement but also indirectly affects performance through

the use of adaptive learning strategies. The current study's results, indicating that student motivation significantly predicts academic performance with a β value of .577, further validate the critical role of motivation. The finding that student motivation accounts for a substantial portion of the variance in academic performance highlights the need for educational policies and practices that prioritize the development of student motivation to improve academic outcomes.

Summary

This section provides a comprehensive summary, conclusions, and recommendations based on the study examining the interplay between socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation as predictors of academic performance among Grade 12 senior high school students.

The study utilized a quantitative method particularly correlational-predictive design to establish the relationship and draw inferences from the influence of the independent variables to the dependent variable of the study.

The results are as follows:

The analysis delves deeply into how twelfth-grade students perceive their families' socioeconomic status, uncovering a prevailing consensus that they come from households with high socioeconomic standing.

Moreover, the study sheds light on the substantial expectations that twelfth-grade students perceive from their parents, emphasizing the weighty role parental aspirations play in shaping their academic journey.

It also highlights the remarkable levels of motivation observed among twelfth-grade students, pointing to a robust link between students' drive and their academic achievements.

In terms of academic performance, the data showcases a noteworthy portion of twelfth-grade students attaining satisfactory or even

outstanding levels, underscoring the overall high standard of achievement within this cohort.

Furthermore, the analysis delves into the intricate interplay between socioeconomic status, parental expectations, student motivation, and academic performance. Despite weak or negligible associations with academic performance, socioeconomic status and parental expectations, student motivation emerges as a key predictor, emphasizing its pivotal role in driving academic success.

Lastly, the regression analysis provides robust confirmation that student motivation significantly influences academic performance among twelfth-grade students, underlining the paramount importance of fostering and sustaining students' intrinsic drive to enhance overall academic outcomes.

Conclusion

In the first section, the analysis delves into the perceptions of socioeconomic status among twelfth-grade students, revealing a consensus of high socioeconomic standing within their families. This perception hints at the likelihood of better academic support and heightened parental expectations; aspects crucial for academic achievement. These findings echo existing studies that underscore the significant influence of socioeconomic status on children's developmental trajectories and academic accomplishments.

Moving on, the discussion shifts towards the notable level of expectations perceived from parents by twelfth-grade students. It suggests that parents commonly set ambitious academic standards for their children, potentially fostering an environment conducive to learning and encouraging students to aim for excellence. This observation aligns with previous research emphasizing the pivotal role parental expectations play in shaping students' academic paths.

Next, attention is drawn to the evident high motivation levels among twelfth-grade students, indicating a strong correlation between

motivation and academic performance. Motivated students are likely to exhibit proactive learning behaviors, resilience in overcoming challenges, and a drive to achieve their goals, factors that contribute positively to academic outcomes. This finding resonates with prior studies highlighting motivation as a key predictor of students' academic success.

The subsequent segment outlines the academic performance of twelfth-grade students, showcasing a significant portion performing at satisfactory or even outstanding levels. This attainment suggests the presence of favorable socioeconomic circumstances, reinforced by high parental expectations and students' intrinsic motivation, all of which likely contribute to their academic achievements. Consistent with previous research, these findings underscore the critical influence of parental support and expectations on maintaining high academic standards.

The analysis further explores the relationship between socioeconomic status, parental expectations, student motivation, and academic performance. While socioeconomic status and parental expectations show weak or insignificant associations with academic performance, student motivation emerges as a significant predictor. This underscores the pivotal role of student motivation in driving academic success, aligning with prior research highlighting its importance in achieving positive educational outcomes.

Lastly, the regression analysis confirms that student motivation significantly predicts academic performance among twelfth-grade students. This emphasizes the substantial impact of motivation on academic success, reinforcing the need to nurture and sustain student motivation to enhance overall academic performance. These findings underscore the critical role of intrinsic motivation in driving academic achievement, echoing existing literature on the subject.

Recommendation

Understanding socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation demonstrates an impact on senior high grade 12 student's academic performance and can inform educators' strategies to support students' success. To further enhance the motivation of senior high grade 12 students, by establishing an honest conversation with parents or guardians about academic goals, interests, and realistic expectations, fostering intrinsic motivation, by utilizing support system from peers, teachers, mentors, and community members, by developing study habits and by embracing mistakes and setbacks as opportunities for learning and improvement are highly recommended to foster success and personal growth.

To strengthen academic performance and increase the senior high grade 12 students' motivation, this study suggests that educators need to avail ongoing professional development opportunities, including seminars and workshops, for better implementation of strategies. Teachers and administrators need to harness intrinsic motivation and foster deeper learning, by creating an engaging and challenging learning experience such as incorporating active learning strategies, and real-world applications to enhance deeper and lifelong learning.

Parents or guardians are encouraged to actively engage with their child's education by regularly communicating with teachers, attending parent-teacher meetings, and monitoring their child's progress. They also need to create a positive learning environment at home by providing resources such as books, educational materials, and a designated study space.

Policymakers need to consider curriculum reforms that promote students' engagement, providing learning opportunities congruent to students' interests and career aspirations to sustain their motivation throughout their academic journey. Resource management for technology integration in education and using instructional materials for educators to offer quality service to students must be considered.

To identify effective strategies for increasing students' motivation and academic performance, policymakers and educators need to invest in research and evaluation. Researchers are suggested to employ mixed-methods approaches combining quantitative measures such as standardized test scores and academic records with qualitative data from interviews, surveys, and observations. Furthermore, navigate into interdisciplinary research initiatives that address the complex interplay between socioeconomic factors, family dynamics, student motivation, and educational outcomes. Ultimately, communicate research findings to policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to support Grade 12 senior high school students in achieving academic success despite the challenges posed by socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and student motivation.

References

- Davis-Kean, P., Tighe, L., & Waters, N. (2020). *The role of parent educational attainment in parenting and children's development*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/ndmxb>
- Davis-Kean, P. E. (2005). The influence of parent education and family income on child achievement: The indirect role of parental expectations and the home environment. *Journal of Family Psychology, 19*(2), 294-304.
- Gottfried, A. E., Fleming, J. S., & Gottfried, A. W. (2001). Continuity of academic intrinsic motivation from childhood through late adolescence: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 93*(1), 3-13.
- Kwarteng, P., Asiamah, F., Twumasi, A. O., Nkansah, J. O., Issaka, J., & Afetorgbor, S. K. (2022). Parental involvement in the academic performance of students in Ghana: Socio-economic status. *Open Journal of Educational Research, 2*(3), 114-125. <https://doi.org/10.31586/ojer.2022.305>
- Lindberg, E. N., Yıldırım, E., Elvan, O., & Öztürk, D. (2019). Parents' educational expectations: Does it matter for academic success? *SDU International Journal of Educational*

Studies, 6(2), 150-160.
<https://doi.org/10.33710/sduijes.596569>

Liquigan, M. L. B., Ortiz, V. I., Sian, D. R. V., & Robles, V. D. (2023). Effects of home environment to the academic performance of the grade 10 students at Sto. Nino National High School, Cagayan, Philippines. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*, 2(1), 31-44.

Long, H., & Pang, W. (2016). Family socioeconomic status, parental expectations, and adolescents' academic achievements: A case of China. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 22(5-6), 283-304.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2016.1237369>

Muhammad, A. S., Bakar, N. A., & Sadiq, A. (2021, December). *Impact of motivation on students' academic performance: A case study of University Sultan Zainal Abidin students*.

Munir, J., Faiza, M., & Daud, S. (2023, June). *The impact of socio-economic status on academic achievement*. Future Training and Services Center Abu Dhabi UAE. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i2.308>

Richardson, M., Abraham, C., & Bond, R. (2012). Psychological correlates of university students' academic performance: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(2), 353-387.

Rumbaoa, L. R. M., San Jose, G. V. O., Sanchez, J. A. L., & Cabauatan, R. R. (2022). Impact of socioeconomic status and parental involvement in students' academic performance of the undergraduate students in a comprehensive university during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Universal Journal of Science and Technology*, 2962-9179.

Sabanal, G. J. A., Reputana, K. D., Palwa, S. S., & Labandero, C. L. H. (2023). Motivation and academic performance of secondary students in science: A correlational study. *Asian Journal of Science Education*, 5(2), 20-29.
<https://doi.org/10.24815/ajse.v5i2.31668>

Şengönül, T. (2022). A review of the relationship between parental involvement and children's academic achievement and the role of family socioeconomic status in this relationship. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 12(2), 32-57.

Tatlah, I. A. (2019). Parental expectations and its impact on academic achievement of students mediated by academic self-concept at secondary level. Paper presented at the *13th International Technology, Education and Development Conference*.
<https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2019.0150>

Yamamoto, Y., & Holloway, S. D. (2010). Parental expectations and children's academic performance in sociocultural context. *Educational Psychology Review*, 22(3), 189-214.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-010-9121-z>